

Germplasm improvement

Genetic resources

International testing of rice hybrids for yield and adaptability by INGER: prospects and problems

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Because of the potential of hybrid rice and its commercial success in China, many countries in Asia, Africa, Latin America, and the Caribbean showed a keen interest in developing and using this technology. The first International Hybrid Rice Observational Nursery (IRHON) was put together in 1994 with 44 hybrids (H), 36 restorers (R), and 5 maintainers (B) developed at IRRI. This nursery was evaluated in Bangladesh (Gazipur), China (Changsha, Hangzhou), India (Coimbatore, Faizabad, Hyderabad, Kapurthala, Karnal, Mandya, Maruteru, Pantnagar), Myanmar (Yangon, Yezin), the Philippines (Los Baños, Maligaya), and Sri Lanka (Batalagoda). A number of hybrids that

could be adapted in most of these countries were identified. Hybrids IR67693H, IR69672H, IR69684H, IR69686H, and IR69689H were identified as superior and widely adapted. In the second IRHON conducted at 29 locations in 13 countries, 33 hybrids, 3 B lines, and 25 R lines developed in IRRI, China, India, and Myanmar were tested. Hybrids IR67693H, IR64616H, IR68284H, IR68877H, IR69679H, and IR70402H were identified as superior. In the third IRHON, three hybrids from a private company were also included. This nursery is now undergoing testing at 45 locations in 16 countries in Asia, Africa, and Latin America.

Superior hybrids in earlier tests produced up to 3 t ha⁻¹ more grain than the best locally adapted check varieties. Genotype × environment (G × E) interaction analysis and superiority analysis helped identify the stability of the hybrids and forecast their adaptability

to untested locations. The G × E analyses did not show a wider adaptability of the hybrids when compared with their parents or checks. INGER, through its global access to hybrids, some parental material, and test sites, can support the testing and use of hybrids and available parents in interested national agricultural systems. INGER can thus help realize the dream of interdependence, exchange, reciprocity, and sharing in a network where no country is too poor to give and no country is too rich to receive. But reservations of some breeders in sharing parental lines and seedborne problems like kernel smut (*Tilletia*) and nematodes impose restrictions. The cost of testing, breeders' rights, and intellectual property rights are some problems that still loom over the scientific community. All these problems could affect the evaluation of hybrids through the INGER mechanism. ■

Screening rice hybrids for quality traits

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In rice hybrids, characters such as lemma and palea, seed size and shape, and pericarp color do not segregate because they are inherited through maternal tissue. Endosperm translucency, chalkiness, and cooking and eating quality traits generally show genetic segregation. Rice is the only cereal consumed as unprocessed whole grain and consumers value specific appearance, taste, and cooking quality traits. Therefore, the effect of heterozygosity of F₁ hybrids on grain quality is more important.

We evaluated 27 hybrids in two replications for 13 physicochemical

characteristics in the 1995 wet season harvest and using standard procedures, including physical parameters such as grain shape and size, endosperm appearance, milling, and head rice recovery (HR%). Among cooking and eating quality traits, we studied amylose content (AC%), gelatinization temperature (GT), water uptake (WU), volume expansion ratio (VER), kernel length after cooking (KLAC), and elongation ratio (ER).

Of the 27 hybrids tested, 17 belonged to long slender, 4 to long bold, 5 to medium slender, and 1 to short bold grain type. Four hybrids—URH1, IR58025A / IR54742, IR58025A / IR34686, and IR58025A / IR32809—possessed extra long grains. Except for URH1, the other three hybrids showed intermediate AC (23.6 and 25.4%). IR58025A / IR34686 exhibited a high VER (5.3). Six hybrids—IR58025A /

IR29723, 3RI-086, MTURH2020, 2RI 158, MTURH2015, and MPH517—recorded a high HR (ranging from 60.3 to 63.9%).

Eleven hybrids were in the most desirable AC range (20–25%) preferred in the Indian subcontinent. IR58025A / IR48751 and IR58025A / IR21567 had typical intermediate AC values (24.9 and 23.3%) with long slender and attractive translucent grains. Other hybrids that possessed an intermediate AC and long slender grains, but with occasional chalkiness, were PA112, HKRH1002, and IR58025A / IR48749.

Hybrids MPH517, 3RI 160, and PMS10A / IR48725 possessed endosperm translucency and high HR. Hybrids with desirable starch properties (intermediate AC) and translucent grains with moderate HR were IR58025A / IR29723, IR58025A / IR34686, IR58025A / IR55838, and